

The Role of The Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in Building Grassroots Culture During the Innovation Period

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in building grassroots culture during the renovation period, thereby clarifying the leadership mechanism and factors affecting the effectiveness of cultural development in the context of urbanization and international integration. Based on an interdisciplinary approach, the study uses methods of document analysis and synthesis, policy analysis, case studies, and comparative analysis, with the main data sources being Party documents, official reports of the City government, and related research works. The research results show that the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee plays a central role in strategic orientation, implementation, and regulation of the process of building grassroots culture. Outstanding achievements include the effective implementation of central government policies, the development of cultural institutions, the promotion of the “National unity in building a culturally rich life” movement, and the gradual formation of distinctive cultural models such as the “Ho Chi Minh Cultural Space”. Simultaneously, the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee has demonstrated its ability to adapt to new trends such as the cultural industry and the creative economy. However, the study also points out some limitations, such as the lack of uniformity in grassroots cultural institutions, the low effectiveness of mobilizing social resources, and challenges in regulating the changing values of urban culture. Based on this, the study proposes innovating leadership methods for modern cultural governance, strengthening socialization, and integrating technological elements to enhance the effectiveness of grassroots cultural development in the context of sustainable development.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the process of national innovation from 1986 to the present, culture has increasingly been identified as the spiritual foundation of society, serving as both a goal and a driving force for sustainable development. This recognition has been consistently affirmed by the Communist Party of Vietnam through its Congresses, especially at the 13th Congress, when it emphasized the requirement of “comprehensive human development, building an advanced Vietnamese culture imbued with national identity” linked to economic development and ensuring social progress and equity (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021). In the context of globalization and profound digital transformation, culture not only plays a role in preserving identity but also becomes an important endogenous resource to enhance national competitiveness and the quality of development.

Based on that foundation, Resolution No. 80-NQ/TW of the Politburo in 2026 continues to affirm the central position of culture in the national development strategy, emphasizing the requirement to build a healthy cultural environment from the grassroots level, considering it the space that directly shapes human personality and strengthens social values (Central Committee - Politburo, 2026; Thanh, 2026). Grassroots culture, as the foundation of cultural life, not only reflects the level of cultural development of a locality but also serves as a “strategic area” in realizing the Party's policies and guidelines on building human

beings and society. Therefore, studying the leadership role of Party organizations, especially the Party committees of large cities like Ho Chi Minh City, in building grassroots culture has profound theoretical and practical significance.

Ho Chi Minh City is the leading economic, cultural, and scientific-technological center of the country. It is a place where traditional and modern cultural values converge and intertwine, and is also a region directly and profoundly impacted by urbanization, globalization, and the market economy. In this context, building grassroots culture is not simply about organizing cultural activities, but also encompasses creating a cultural environment, building a civilized urban lifestyle, developing a system of cultural institutions, and strengthening social and moral values. As Pham Ngoc Hoa (2021) pointed out, building a civilized urban lifestyle in Ho Chi Minh City is a comprehensive process requiring close coordination between state management, community participation, and the guiding role of the Party organization.

In particular, over three decades of innovation, the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee has demonstrated comprehensive leadership in implementing cultural policies from the central to local levels, while proactively creating many models suitable to the city's characteristics. Movements such as “All citizens unite to build a cultured life” have become pillars in building grassroots culture, contributing to improving the quality of people's spiritual lives and strengthening national unity (Ho Chi Minh City People's Committee, 2021 & 2025). The achievements are not only reflected in the expansion of the scope and depth of cultural activities but also in the transformation of cultural awareness and behavior within the community.

However, alongside these achievements, the process of building grassroots culture in Ho Chi Minh City is also facing many challenges. The rapid development of urbanization and the market economy has given rise to complex changes in cultural values, leading to the risk of declining moral standards and an increase in deviant phenomena in social life. At the same time, the system of grassroots cultural institutions is still not synchronized, its operational efficiency is not high, and it does not fully meet the increasingly diverse cultural needs of the people (Chinh, 2023; Linh, 2021). Dinh Van Hien (2023) also argues that the role of grassroots cultural institutions is still limited due to a lack of resources, inflexible management mechanisms, and ineffective community participation.

In this context, the role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee becomes even more important in guiding, regulating, and leading the process of building grassroots culture in a sustainable direction and in line with the requirements of the new era. The construction of the “Ho Chi Minh cultural space”, linked to the protection of the Party's ideological foundation, is a clear example of this effort to create a distinctive cultural environment that both inherits traditional values and adapts to the modern context (Hiep, 2024). At the same time, policies for developing the cultural industry and cultural economy also require restructuring the approach to grassroots culture, shifting from “administrative management” to “cultural governance” in an open, creative, and integrated direction (Hieu, 2026).

From a theoretical perspective, studying the role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in building grassroots culture clarifies the operational mechanism of the political system in the cultural field, particularly the relationship among Party leadership, State management, and social participation. Simultaneously, this research also contributes to supplementing the scientific arguments for the development of grassroots culture. Improving cultural policies in the new context, where culture is increasingly closely linked to economic, technological and social governance fields. As Bui Hoai Son (2025) emphasized, building grassroots cultural life in the new era requires an integrated approach, taking people as the center and maximizing the role of the community.

From a practical perspective, this research is significant in objectively evaluating the achievements, limitations, and causes in the process of building grassroots culture in Ho Chi Minh City, thereby proposing solutions to improve the effectiveness of the Party Committee's leadership in this field. At the same time, the lessons learned from Ho Chi Minh City's practical experience can also serve as a reference for other localities nationwide in implementing cultural policies appropriate to their specific conditions.

From the issues mentioned above, it can be seen that the research on “The Role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in Building Grassroots Culture in the Innovation Era” is not only significant academically but also has high practical value, contributing to clarifying the role of the Party organization in cultural development, a field that is increasingly central to the nation's sustainable development strategy.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE RESEARCH SITUATION

2.1. Evaluating the results of research works

In recent years, the issue of building grassroots culture and the role of the political system in this field has attracted the attention of many researchers, policymakers, and management agencies. Research works can be divided into three main groups: (i) research on the Party's views and guidelines on cultural development; (ii) research on grassroots cultural institutions and life; and (iii) research on the practical aspects of building culture in Ho Chi Minh City.

First, at the theoretical and policy-oriented level, many works have clarified the Party's consistent viewpoint on the position and role of culture in sustainable development. The Party's 13th Congress documents affirm that culture is the spiritual foundation of society and also an important endogenous driving force of development (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021). Based on that, Resolution No. 80-NQ/TW of 2026 continues to emphasize the requirement to build a healthy cultural environment from the grassroots level, considering this as the space that directly shapes human personality and strengthens the national value system

(Central Committee - Politburo, 2026; Thanh, 2026). Studies such as that of Nguyen Van Hung (2026) have broadened the approach by placing the issue of cultural development in the context of the new era, linked to digital transformation, the creative economy, and international integration. At the same time, Do Thi Huong Giang (2021) also contributed to clarifying the requirement of “unity in diversity” of Vietnamese culture, thereby emphasizing the flexibility and adaptability of culture in modern development conditions.

In the second group of studies, the works focus on analyzing the system of grassroots cultural institutions and community cultural life. Tran Minh Chinh (2023) pointed out the uneven development of the grassroots cultural institution system, from physical infrastructure to operational mechanisms, and proposed solutions to improve operational efficiency. Similarly, Dinh Van Hien (2023) emphasized the role of cultural institutions as a “soft infrastructure” in building cultural life, while also pointing out limitations in resources, management mechanisms, and community participation. Nguyen Thi My Linh (2021) approached the issue from a management perspective, arguing that the effectiveness of using cultural institutions largely depends on management capacity and coordination mechanisms among stakeholders. Notably, Bui Hoai Son (2025) presented a new approach, viewing the building of grassroots cultural life in the new era as a multi-dimensional integrated process, in which people are both the center and the subject of cultural creation.

The third research group focuses on the practice of building culture in Ho Chi Minh City, a special urban area with many unique economic, social, and cultural characteristics. Works such as those by Pham Ngoc Hoa (2021) have deeply analyzed the process of building a cultural and civilized urban lifestyle, pointing out positive changes as well as challenges in forming urban behavioral norms. Minh Hiep (2024) mentions the construction of a “Ho Chi Minh cultural space” as an important orientation to link cultural development with protecting the ideological foundation of the Party. Vu Phong (2024), through identifying six tasks for cultural and human development in Ho Chi Minh City, has contributed to clarifying the local strategic orientation in the new period.

Furthermore, the summary reports of the Ho Chi Minh City People's Committee (2021 & 2025) on the “All People Unite to Build a Culturally Rich Life” movement have provided important practical data, comprehensively reflecting the implementation of cultural policies at the grassroots level over more than two decades. These documents show the widespread impact of the movement, while also pointing out limitations in quality, sustainability, and the level of public participation. In addition, recent studies on the development of the cultural industry (Hieu, 2026) and the building of urban civilization (Tuyet, 2020) have expanded the scope of research, showing a shift from a traditional approach to a modern one, linking culture with the economy and urban governance.

Overall, the research has achieved significant results. Firstly, a relatively solid theoretical foundation has been established regarding the role of culture and grassroots culture in social development. Secondly, the current state of the cultural institution system and community cultural life has been clarified, thereby proposing many practical solutions. Thirdly, it has initially reflected the specific characteristics of cultural development in Ho Chi Minh City, especially in the context of urbanization and international integration.

2.2. Gaps and research directions

Despite achieving many noteworthy results, current research still has some gaps that need further clarification:

Firstly, most studies have only focused on policy analysis or describing the current situation, without delving into clarifying the leadership role of local Party committees in building grassroots culture as a systematic whole. Studies often approach the issue from a piecemeal perspective, focusing on aspects such as cultural institutions, civilized lifestyles, or mass movements, without considering the overall relationship between Party leadership, State management, and social participation. This leads to a lack of a comprehensive analytical framework for the functioning of the political system in the cultural sphere.

Secondly, while studies on Ho Chi Minh City are rich in practical aspects, they lack in-depth theoretical analysis, particularly regarding the role of the City Party Committee within the unique context of a large, culturally diverse metropolis heavily influenced by globalization. Issues such as the transformation of value systems, cultural conflicts, and the impact of the market economy on grassroots cultural life have not yet been systematically and thoroughly studied.

Thirdly, in the new context with the emergence of trends such as digital transformation, cultural industries, and the creative economy, current research has not yet updated and integrated these elements into the analysis of grassroots culture. As Resolution No. 80-NQ/TW emphasized, cultural development in the new era requires an Innovation approach, closely linking culture with technology, economics, and social governance (Central Committee - Politburo, 2026). However, this gap has not yet been filled in existing research.

Based on the above gaps, the research “The Role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in Building Grassroots Culture in the Innovation Era” aims to build a comprehensive analytical framework on the leadership role of the Party Committee in the cultural field, integrating theoretical and practical elements. This research not only focuses on clarifying the leadership mechanisms and organizational implementation methods but also analyzes the influencing factors and conditions ensuring the development of grassroots culture in the new context.

At the same time, the research aims to supplement the scientific basis for cultural policy planning at the local level, especially in building a healthy cultural environment, developing an effective system of cultural institutions, and improving the quality of cultural life for the people. Through this, it contributes to clarifying the role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee as a central entity in the process of creating and developing grassroots culture, meeting the requirements of sustainable development in the era of Innovation and international integration.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To clarify the role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in building grassroots culture in the Innovation era, this research is conducted based on a combination of interdisciplinary research methods, ensuring scientific rigor, objectivity, and suitability to the specific characteristics of the cultural policy field.

Firstly, the method of document analysis and synthesis is used as the main foundation. The research collects, systematizes, and analyzes Party documents, especially the documents of the 13th National Congress (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021) and Resolution No. 80-NQ/TW of the Politburo in 2026, to clarify the viewpoints and strategic orientations on cultural development in the new context. Simultaneously, scientific research works, specialized articles, and summary reports of the People's Committee of Ho Chi Minh City (2021 & 2025) are also utilized to build the theoretical and practical basis for the topic. Through this method, the research establishes an analytical framework on grassroots culture and the leadership role of the local Party committee.

Secondly, policy analysis methods are applied to clarify the content, objectives, and implementation mechanisms of cultural policies in Ho Chi Minh City. Based on the “Strategy for the Development of the Cultural Sector in Ho Chi Minh City period 2020–2035” (Ho Chi Minh City People's Committee, 2021), the study assesses the degree of compatibility between central government policies and their implementation at the local level, while also analyzing the policy tools used in building grassroots culture.

Thirdly, the case study method is applied to Ho Chi Minh City as a typical example of a special urban area. This case study allows for in-depth analysis of the unique economic, social, and cultural characteristics, as well as how the City Party Committee implements cultural policies in the context of urbanization and international integration. Contents such as building a “Ho Chi Minh cultural space” (Hiep, 2024) or developing the cultural industry (Hieu, 2026) are considered as concrete evidence of the Party Committee's leadership role.

Fourthly, the comparative method is used to identify the differences between theory and practice, between policy objectives and implementation results. Through comparing the results achieved in the “all people unite to build a culturally rich life” movement across different stages (Ho Chi Minh City People's Committee, 2021 & 2025), the study assesses the effectiveness and sustainability of grassroots cultural activities.

Fifthly, a systems and interdisciplinary approach is applied throughout the research, considering the building of grassroots culture as a holistic process influenced by many factors such as politics, economics, society, and technology. This approach allows for clarifying the relationship between Party leadership, State management, and community participation, thereby providing comprehensive assessments and recommendations that are appropriate to the requirements of cultural development in the new era.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. The strategic orientation role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in building grassroots culture

The research results show that, during the Innovation period, the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee played a central role in strategically orienting the development of grassroots culture, clearly demonstrated through the concretization of the Central Committee's viewpoints into action programs suitable to the urban characteristics.

On a theoretical level, culture is defined as the spiritual foundation of society, both a goal and a driving force for development (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021). This perspective was further developed in Resolution No. 80-NQ/TW of 2026, which emphasized building a cultural environment from the grassroots level as a prerequisite for holistic human development (Central Committee - Politburo, 2026). Based on this, the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee proactively transformed macro-level orientations into specific strategies, notably the “Strategy for the Development of the Cultural Sector in Ho Chi Minh City, period 2020–2035” (Ho Chi Minh City People's Committee, 2021).

A noteworthy point is the shift in cultural leadership thinking from “administrative management” to “creating a cultural environment”. This is reflected in the fact that the City Party Committee not only organizes cultural activities but also emphasizes building a system of values, behavioral norms, and distinctive cultural spaces. The development of the “Ho Chi Minh cultural space” is a clear example, aiming to create a symbolic cultural ecosystem that connects Ho Chi Minh's thought with contemporary life (Hiep, 2024).

In addition, the City Party Committee also demonstrates its guiding role in integrating culture into other development areas such as economics, urban development, and technology. Promoting cultural industries and the creative economy not only expands the scope of culture but also contributes to increasing the added value and competitiveness of the city (Hieu, 2026). This aligns with international trends where culture is increasingly becoming a pillar in sustainable development (Hung, 2026).

Thus, the research results confirm that the role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee is not limited to leading the implementation of policies, but also includes shaping the vision, creating the space, and guiding the transformation of the grassroots cultural development model in the new context.

4.2. The role of organizing implementation and mobilizing resources in building grassroots culture

One of the outstanding results is the role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in organizing implementation and mobilizing resources for building grassroots culture.

First of all, the City Party Committee has effectively promoted the coordination mechanism between the levels of government, political and social organizations, and the community. The “All people unite to build a cultured life” movement is a typical example of this approach. According to reports from the People's Committee of Ho Chi Minh City (2021 & 2025), the movement has achieved widespread dissemination, contributing to raising community awareness, strengthening moral values, and building a healthy cultural environment at the grassroots level.

Secondly, the City Party Committee has focused on developing a system of grassroots cultural institutions such as cultural centers, cultural and sports centers, community libraries, etc. These are considered “soft infrastructure” playing an important role in organizing cultural activities and improving the spiritual life of the people (Hien, 2023). However, research results also indicate that the effectiveness of these institutions largely depends on management capacity and the level of community participation (Linh, 2021).

A noteworthy point is the shift in the method of mobilizing resources, from relying primarily on the state budget to diversifying social resources. The socialization of cultural activities has helped expand the scale and improve the quality of cultural activities, while creating conditions for non-state entities to participate in the cultural development process.

In addition, the City Party Committee also focuses on integrating cultural goals into urban development programs, especially building a civilized urban lifestyle. Studies show that the formation of cultural behavioral norms in urban spaces is a complex process, requiring close coordination between policy and practice (Hoa, 2021).

Therefore, it can be seen that the role of the City Party Committee is not only reflected in its orientation but also in its ability to organize implementation and effectively mobilize social resources for building grassroots culture.

4.3. The role of regulating and adapting to cultural change in the context of urbanization and integration

Research results show that, in the context of rapid urbanization and deep international integration, the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee plays a crucial role in regulating and adapting to cultural changes.

On the one hand, the process of urbanization and the market economy have created profound changes in cultural values, leading to the diversification of norms and lifestyles. This poses a major challenge in maintaining cultural identity and ensuring unity in diversity (Giang, 2021). In this context, the City Party Committee has implemented many solutions to orient values and strengthen cultural norms, especially through education, media, and social movements.

On the other hand, the City Party Committee also demonstrates the ability to flexibly adapt to new trends such as digital transformation and the creative economy. The development of the cultural industry is not only an economic strategy but also a new method for preserving and promoting cultural values in the modern context (Hieu, 2026). This shows a shift from a “static preservation” mindset to a “dynamic development” mindset in cultural management.

At the same time, the construction of the Ho Chi Minh cultural space is also an innovative approach to connecting the past with the present, between tradition and modernity, thereby creating a distinctive urban cultural identity (Hiep, 2024).

However, the research also indicates that the process of regulating culture still faces many difficulties, especially in controlling deviant phenomena and ensuring a balance between economic development and cultural preservation. This requires the City Party Committee to continue innovating leadership methods, improving forecasting capacity, and adapting to social changes.

4.4. Achievements, limitations, and challenges

A synthesis of research results shows that the role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in building grassroots culture during the Innovation period has achieved many important accomplishments.

First, regarding achievements, the City Party Committee has built a relatively synchronized cultural policy system, consistent with the Central Government's orientation and local characteristics. Grassroots cultural movements have been widely implemented, contributing to improving the spiritual life of the people and strengthening national unity. At the same time, the integration of culture into economic and urban development has opened up new directions for sustainable development.

However, alongside these achievements, many limitations still exist. The system of grassroots cultural institutions is not yet truly synchronized, and its operational efficiency is still not high (Tran Minh Chinh, 2023). Community participation in some cultural activities remains largely superficial and has not truly fostered its role as the main actor. Furthermore, issues such as declining moral standards and increasing deviant behaviors in urban life remain significant challenges.

In particular, in the new context, building grassroots culture is facing increasingly high demands for creativity, adaptability, and sustainability. This requires the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee to continue innovating its thinking and leadership methods, shifting from “management” to “cultural governance”, from “administrative” to “socialization” and “creativeization”.

From the above analysis, it can be affirmed that the role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in building grassroots culture is not only a decisive factor for the development of local culture but also has important reference significance for other cities nationwide. This also serves as a basis for further in-depth research on the model of cultural leadership in the context of digital transformation and international integration.

5. CONCLUSION

This study has clarified the central and decisive role of the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee in building grassroots culture during the Innovation period, through four main aspects: strategic orientation, implementation, adaptation and regulation, and cultural environment creation. The results show that the City Party Committee not only plays a leading role in concretizing the Central Committee's policies but also demonstrates proactiveness and creativity in building cultural models suitable to the urban characteristics, such as developing the “Ho Chi Minh cultural space” and promoting the cultural industry. However, the study also points out notable limitations, including the lack of synchronization in the system of grassroots cultural institutions, the inadequate effectiveness of mobilizing social resources, and the challenges in regulating changes in cultural values in the context of urbanization and globalization. These issues highlight the urgent need to innovate leadership methods towards modern cultural governance, integrating policy, technology, and community participation. Theoretically, the research contributes to supplementing the analytical framework on the role of Party organizations in developing grassroots culture in the context of social transformation. Practically, the research results provide scientific arguments for improving cultural policies in large cities. In the future, further research should be expanded in the direction of cross-city comparisons and the integration of digital transformation elements to enhance the effectiveness of building sustainable grassroots culture.

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